

Interfacial stability of CoSb₃ in contact with chromium: Reactive diffusion and microstructure evolution

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ABSTRACT

Reliability of thermoelectric devices strongly depends on the stability of structural materials at the interfaces. In this work reactivity and diffusion in a Cr–CoSb₃ couple under vacuum were systematically studied. Diffusion couples were produced by magnetron sputtering of chromium onto CoSb₃ substrates. The experimental procedure involved isothermal annealing of the diffusion couples sealed in the evacuated quartz ampules in the temperature range 500 °C–600 °C for time intervals up to 288 h. Different techniques of electron microscopy and spectroscopy were employed to evaluate the extent of reactive diffusion. Transport processes and chemical reactions involved in the formation of an interdiffusion zone were assessed. In all samples this zone was layered and composed of Co–Cr antimonides with different proportions of transition metals. To visualize the complex structure of the interdiffusion zone, a 3D model was created using focused ion beam – scanning electron microscopy (FIB–SEM) tomography. It was found that its growth kinetics followed a parabolic rate law. The calculated parabolic rate constants, *k*, for the innermost layer composed of (Co,Cr)Sb₂ were $4.3 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, $1.5 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ and $3.6 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, and for the outermost layer composed of (Cr,Co)Sb $1.2 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, $4.4 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ and $9.4 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ at 500 °C, 550 °C and 600 °C, respectively. Activation energies, *Q*, for the layer growth of (Co,Cr)Sb₂ and (Cr,Co)Sb were $118.7 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and $114.5 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively. Finally, consecutive stages of the interdiffusion zone formation were explained.

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1. Introduction

Thermoelectric materials have high potential as alternative energy sources due to the capability of converting waste heat directly into electricity [1–12]. Conversion efficiency can be described by temperature-dependence of a dimensionless figure of merit (*ZT*) which combines Seebeck coefficient (α), electrical conductivity (σ) and thermal conductivity (λ): $ZT = \alpha^2 \cdot \sigma \cdot \lambda^{-1} \cdot T$. Currently the most efficient thermoelectrics are based on semiconductors. Materials under investigation for power generation systems comprise skutterudites [13–18], silicides [19–23], half-Heusler compounds [24–26], tellurides [27–32] or ceramics [33–39]. It is known that thermoelectric properties of these materials are strongly dependent on exact chemical composition. Even a small deviation from

stoichiometry can cause a significant drop in thermoelectric performance. Unfortunately, since thermoelectrics often work at elevated temperatures, they undergo changes in chemical composition as a result of diffusion around interfaces. Thermal stability of interfaces, including electrical connections and protective coatings, is likely to be one of the key issues for an efficient thermoelectric conversion [40–51]. However, most researchers report worsening of thermoelectric properties without an in-depth analysis of its origin, mainly related to diffusion processes.

In this work interfacial stability of a thermoelectric material/metal system was studied using CoSb₃–Cr couples. Phenomena occurring at the CoSb₃/Cr interface are particularly important for the lifetime of some oxidation resistant coatings on the CoSb₃-based components of thermoelectric modules. Cobalt triantimonide exhibits the highest thermoelectric performance in the temperature range 400–700 °C [1]. As shown recently [52], thin Cr–Si coatings can provide a satisfactory protection against its

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Fig. 1. SEM–SE images of the Cr–CoSb₃ diffusion couple after annealing at 600 °C for 24 h presenting consecutive FIB–SEM milling steps: cross-section of the sample before milling (a), protective platinum layer deposited on the area of interest (b), view of sample during sectioning (c). The surrounding material was removed by FIB milling to provide undisturbed view during sectioning.

oxidation. For a thorough understanding of the system stability, protection mechanism and durability, this study was focused on the reactivity and diffusion in the Cr–CoSb₃ system under vacuum.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Diffusion couples

The substrate material, CoSb₃, was produced by combustion synthesis, followed by grinding and sintering according to the procedure described previously [53]. Surface finish involved grinding on silicon carbide papers up to 1500 grit and degreasing in acetone. Pulsed magnetron sputtering technique was used to deposit Cr layers on the CoSb₃ substrate. The deposition process was conducted in an argon atmosphere ($7.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar) for 30 min, the substrate was maintained at 200 °C. The average coating thickness

was about 2.5 μm. Next the samples were isothermally annealed in the evacuated quartz ampoules at the temperature of 500 °C, 550 °C or 600 °C for time intervals ranging from 1 h to 288 h. The ampoules with the diffusion couples were inserted into the hot furnace and rapidly cooled to the room temperature after the desired dwell time.

2.2. Examination methods

Microstructure, chemical composition and phase composition of the diffusion couples were systematically examined, using scanning, transmission/scanning-transmission and high-resolution scanning-transmission electron microscopy (SEM, TEM/STEM, HR-STEM, respectively) combined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The surfaces and cross-sections were analysed using a high-resolution scanning electron microscope Merlin Gemini

Fig. 2. SEM images of Cr–CoSb₃ diffusion couples annealed at 500 °C (a), 550 °C (b) and 600 °C (c) for 24 h and approximate concentration of Co, Cr and Sb (by SEM–EDS) in points 1–6 (d) marked in Fig. 2 c.

Fig. 3. SEM-BSE image of the Cr–CoSb₃ diffusion couple after annealing at 600 °C for 24 h with Co, Sb and Cr concentration profiles along the solid line marked above and EDS maps of selected chemical elements distribution in the interdiffusion zone. Colors in the first map: violet – (Cr,Co)Sb, green – (Co,Cr)Sb, yellow – (Co,Cr)Sb₂, orange – CoSb₃. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

II (ZEISS) equipped with a field-emission gun (FEG) and Quantax 800 microanalysis system (Bruker). For the TEM/STEM observation a thin lamella was prepared by means of a focused ion beam (FIB) NEON CrossBeam 40 EsB (ZEISS). A high-resolution TEM/STEM analysis of the interdiffusion zone was performed using the probe Cs-corrected Titan3 G2 60–300 with the ChemiSTEM™ system (FEI) [54]. A high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector was used for imaging in a HR-STEM mode. The chemical composition was determined by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (STEM-EDS). Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) combined with JEMS software [55] allowed phase identification.

2.3. FIB-SEM tomography

To investigate structural features of the interdiffusion zone, a serial sectioning procedure was employed for 3D imaging with the aid of FIB-SEM tomography technique [56–58]. The selected representative Cr–CoSb₃ diffusion couple was one annealed at 600 °C for 24 h. The methodology is based on progressive removal of equal-thickness material layers using a focused ion beam and recording an image after each milling cycle. Consecutive milling steps are presented in Fig. 1a–c. The adjusted milling parameters using a dual-beam NEON CrossBeam 40EsB (ZEISS) microscope

were the following: Ga⁺ ion source, beam current of 1 nA, accelerating voltage of 30 kV and step thickness of 45 nm. After every step the image of the exposed surface was recorded in the back-scattered electrons contrast (BSE) and secondary electrons contrast (SE) at 3.0 kV accelerating voltage with a voxel size of 15 × 15 × 45 nm. Roughly a 13 × 7 × 5 μm volume was reconstructed using the ImageJ 1.44p and Avizo Fire 6.0 software.

2.4. Growth kinetics

Kinetic parameters of the diffusion process were calculated from thickness changes of the interdiffusion layers over time at constant temperature. Because of irregular thickness of the layers, the mean value was estimated from 20 random measurements on SEM images. Thickness of the layers formed by reactive diffusion can be expressed as follows:

$$X = X_0 + (kt)^n, \quad (1)$$

where t is the reaction time, X is the layer thickness at time t , X_0 is the initial layer thickness, k is the rate constant dependent on temperature and n is the time exponent. If reactive diffusion is the rate-controlling step, the layer thickness should increase according

Table 1
Selected properties of cobalt and chromium antimonides [39–65].

Compound	Space group	Lattice parameters (room temp.) [Å]	T _{melt} [°C]	Nonstoichiometry range at 500 °C – 600 °C [at.%]	Enthalpy of formation Δ _f H° [kJ·mol ⁻¹]	Gibbs free energy of formation Δ _f G° [kJ·mol ⁻¹]
CoSb ₃	Im-3 (204)	a = b = c = 0.903	876	stoichiometric	–63.0 (527 °C) –63.2 (627 °C)	–58.9 (527 °C) –58.6 (600 °C) –58.4 (627 °C)
CoSb ₂	P2 ₁ /c (14)	a = 0.652 b = 0.638 c = 0.655	931	Co 64.0–66.0	–50.5 (527 °C) –50.5 (627 °C)	–49.5 (527 °C) –49.5 (600 °C) –49.4 (627 °C)
CoSb	P6 ₃ /mmc (194)	a = b = 0.391 c = 0.519	1202	Co 49.0–51.0	–41.6 (527 °C) –41.5 (627 °C)	–38.9 (527 °C) –37.6 (600 °C) –38.5 (627 °C)
CrSb ₂	I4/mcm (140)	a = 0.601 b = 0.686 c = 0.327	718	stoichiometric	–18.6 (25 °C) –15.7 (577 °C)	–18.7 (25 °C) –21.4 (577 °C)
CrSb	P6 ₃ /mmc (194)	a = b = 0.415 c = 0.552	1113	Cr 49.0–50.0	–5.2 (25 °C) 5.8 (577 °C)	–17.4 (577 °C)

Fig. 4. STEM-HAADF image of the interdiffusion zone at the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ grain boundary triple junction with the STEM-EDS elemental maps (a); concentration profiles of Co, Sb and Cr across the phase boundaries: line 1 (b), line 2 (c), line 3 (d).

to a parabolic rate law with $n = 0.5$. The parabolic rate constant k was determined from the slope of the regression line in a layer thickness squared vs. time plot.

The activation energy Q and the parabolic rate constant relationship can be expressed by the Arrhenius equation:

$$k = k_0 \cdot e^{(-Q/RT)}, \quad (2)$$

where T is the absolute temperature in K, R is the gas constant, $8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ and k_0 is a pre-exponential factor. The Q values were calculated using the slope of the regression line in the

Arrhenius co-ordinate system, $\ln k$ against T^{-1} .

The values of k and Q with the standard deviations and the related adjusted coefficients of determination R^2_{adj} were calculated using the OriginLab 2017 software.

3. Results

3.1. Microstructure, chemical and phase composition

Interactions between the chromium layer and the CoSb₃ substrate were examined on the basis of isothermal annealing in an

Fig. 5. The indexed TEM-SAED patterns of the regions marked with circles in Fig. 4a: CoSb₂ recorded at the ZA [001] (double diffraction) (a), CrSb recorded at ZA [214] (b), CoSb recorded at ZA [101] (c), ring pattern for region 3 (d).

oxygen-free environment. After annealing at 500 °C, 550 °C and 600 °C, a layered interdiffusion zone was observed. Depending on the applied time-temperature conditions, the phase composition and thickness of the individual layers were different, as presented in Fig. 2a–d. The first layer which appeared at the Cr/CoSb₃ interface consisted of Cr, Sb and Co (Fig. 2a–c and 3). It is described as (Cr,Co)Sb, i.e. Co-doped CrSb, being a predominant phase in this

layer. Concentration of Co in CrSb increased with the annealing time and after more than 18 h, regardless of the temperature, cobalt concentration in this phase was not higher than 10 at.%, as illustrated in Fig. 3 showing the Co, Sb and Cr concentration profiles across the interdiffusion zone of the sample annealed for 24 h at 600 °C. At shorter annealing times, the concentration of cobalt was below the detection limit. The second layer was observed in

Fig. 6. STEM-HAADF image of the interdiffusion zone at the (Co,Cr)Sb₂/CoSb₃ interface with the STEM-EDS elemental maps.

specimens heated for at least 18 h, independently of the experimental temperature. According to the SEM-EDS analysis (Fig. 3) this layer contained Sb at about 67 at.%, Co at about 31 at.% and Cr at about 2 at.%, which suggested that it was composed of CoSb_2 with some Co atoms replaced by Cr, and accordingly it was described as $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$. In the second layer a Cr-rich phase was locally detected in the $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ matrix (Fig. 2a–c and 3). Its chemical composition was approximately the same as that of the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ phase in the first layer. Some fluctuations visible in Fig. 3, where Co concentration in the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ grain reaches 15 at.%, originate from insufficient resolution of the EDS analysis rather than a real difference in chemical composition.

The phase composition of the interdiffusion zone was confirmed by STEM-SAED analyses. Selected properties of cobalt and chromium antimonides thermodynamically possible in the investigated system are listed in Table 1. Fig. 4a presents a STEM-HAADF image of the interdiffusion zone at the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}/(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ interface with the STEM-EDS elemental maps for the sample annealed at 600 °C for 24 h. The SAED analysis of the regions marked with circles in Fig. 4a are presented in Fig. 5a–d. The SAED pattern from region 1 recorded at the [001] zone axis (ZA) corresponds to CoSb_2 (Fig. 5a) and that from region 2 recorded at [214] zone axis corresponds to CrSb. The concentration profiles of chemical elements across the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}/(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ interface (line 3 in Fig. 4a) are presented in Fig. 4d.

The analyses of concentration and distribution of chemical elements in the interdiffusion zone revealed an additional phase occurring locally at the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}/(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ interface (Figs. 3 and 4a–b), i.e. one containing Co, Cr and Sb with the atomic ratio close to 4:1:5, hereinafter referred to as $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}$. The TEM-SAED pattern taken from this region is presented in Fig. 5c and d; the spots corresponding to the CoSb phase were recorded at [101] zone axis (Fig. 5c). The rings in this pattern were also ascribed to CoSb (Fig. 5d). As CrSb and CoSb have the same crystal structure, a theoretical pattern for CrSb is also shown in Fig. 5d to illustrate the differences. Doping in the transition metal position causes changes in the values of lattice parameters and results in the expansion or contraction of the measured electron diffraction pattern. However, as shown in Ref. [66], differences in the values of lattice parameters at room temperature at the doping level measured in this study (Co-doping of CrSb at a level of about 5 at.% and Cr-doping of CoSb at a level of about 10 at.%) are on the second or third decimal place. As a result, the diffraction patterns for $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}$ match almost perfectly the theoretical ones for CrSb and CoSb , respectively (Fig. 5b–d). The STEM-EDS concentration profiles across the $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}/(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ (line 1 in Fig. 4a) and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}/(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ (line 2 in Fig. 4a) interfaces are presented in Fig. 4b and c, respectively.

According to the SEM-EDS analyses (Figs. 2d and 3), chromium was not found in CoSb_3 . The STEM-HAADF image with the STEM-EDS elemental maps at the $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2/\text{CoSb}_3$ interface is presented in Fig. 6. Fig. 7a and b shows the TEM-SAED patterns from the $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ (ZA [–111]) and CoSb_3 (ZA [101]) grains.

High-resolution images of the interdiffusion zone at the interface with CoSb_3 taken at different orientations for CoSb_3 and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ grains, are presented in Fig. 8 a–c. The phases were identified based on the Fourier transform (FFT) of high-resolution images (Fig. 8 d–f) and corresponding simulations of the HR-STEM images (insets). In the case of CoSb_3 , identification was based on the analysis of images taken at two different ZA, due to a very large mismatch (close to 20%) of the lattice parameters at ZA [101] (Fig. 8 d). The FFT pattern of the HR-STEM image taken from the same grain at ZA [313] fitted well and mismatch was in a range of a few percent. Mismatch of the lattice parameters indicates large stresses in the grains close to the interface, which also can be observed on

the STEM image of the interface (inset in Fig. 8 a). Since the preparation of a thin enough lamella for high-resolution imaging of the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}/(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}/(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ triple junction failed, it is believed that strong stresses were also present between different phases in the interdiffusion zone.

It should be also noted, that after shorter experiments, i.e. annealing at 550 °C for up to 3 h and at 600 °C for up to 12 h, another phase with the composition corresponding to CrSb_2 (Sb ~67 at.%, Cr up to 33 at.%) was observed in the interdiffusion zone (Fig. 9a–c). After annealing at 600 °C for 12 h the CrSb_2 layer had thickness of a few micrometers (Fig. 9c).

Fig. 7. Indexed TEM-SAED patterns of the regions marked with circles in Fig. 6: CoSb_2 recorded at the [–111] zone axis (double diffraction) (a), CoSb_3 recorded at [101] zone axis (b).

Fig. 8. HR-STEM images of interdiffusion zone/CoSb₃ interface: oriented to the ZA [101] of CoSb₃ grain (a) and its magnification (b); oriented to the ZA [313] of (Co,Cr)Sb₂ grain (c). Small square in the inset in fig. (a) indicates region of analyse. HR-STEM images of CoSb₃ at ZA [101] (d) and at ZA [313] (e), (Co,Cr)Sb₂ [231] (f) with corresponding HR-STEM image simulations (insets). Right-bottom insets present indexed Fourier transform (FFT) patterns of (d)–(f) HR/STEM images.

FIB-SEM tomography technique was used to construct a spatial model of the interdiffusion zone. The 3D reconstruction based on a stack of BSE images is shown in Fig. 10. A significant volume of material ($13.4 \times 6.7 \times 5.0 \mu\text{m}$) was subjected to the 3D microstructure reconstruction and measurements of individual phases. As the BSE images had rather poor contrast, the location of CoSb₃ was determined using the SE images. The 3D reconstructed volume showing spatial distribution of individual phases is presented in Fig. 11. Both, the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ and (Co,Cr)Sb₂/CoSb₃ interfaces are non-uniform. The (Co,Cr)Sb grains are found exclusively at the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ interface. The calculated overall volume contributions of the phases present in the interdiffusion zone and its porosity are listed in Table 2. It should be noted that porosity includes the volume of cracks visible in the SEM images (Figs. 2 and 3) and in the 3D reconstruction (Fig. 12b). The origin of these cracks is not fully clear, as they can result from unmatched coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) as well as from sample cutting or grinding. The amount of (Cr,Co)Sb in the (Co,Cr)Sb₂ phase was determined as about 6 vol%. Moreover, the 3D reconstruction revealed that the (Cr,Co)Sb grains present within the (Co,Cr)Sb₂

layer were not interconnected (Fig. 12a).

3.2. Growth kinetics

SEM images of the selected diffusion couples in Fig. 13 present evolution of the interdiffusion zone thickness up to 288 h. In the first approximation it was assumed that phase composition and thickness of two distinct layers, (Co,Cr)Sb₂ and (Cr,Co)Sb, were uniform. Such assumption results in a relatively high standard deviation, exceeding 10%. To verify the reliability of results based on thickness measurements, the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ volume fraction was calculated using data from the 3D reconstruction (Table 2) and compared with the thickness ratio of the layers in the corresponding experimental conditions. The obtained volume fraction (0.52) and thickness ratio (0.53) were almost equal, which confirmed correctness of the approach. The changes of layer thickness vs. time are presented in Fig. 14a–c.

In the next step the parabolic rate constants k and the activation energy Q of the layer growth were determined.

The parabolic rate constants k at different temperatures were

Fig. 9. Cross-section SEM, BSE images of Cr–CoSb₃ diffusion couples annealed at 600 °C for 3 h (a), 6 h (b) and 12 h (c).

Fig. 10. Interdiffusion zone reconstruction based on stack of SEM-BSE images.

Fig. 11. 3D reconstruction of interdiffusion zone: yellow – (Cr,Co)Sb, green – CoSb, red – (Co,Cr)Sb₂, blue – CoSb₃. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 2
Composition of the analysed segment of the interdiffusion zone.

Phase [vol%]	
CoSb ₃	2.2
(Co,Cr)Sb ₂	60.0
(Cr,Co)Sb	31.2
CoSb	0.2
Porosity	6.4
(Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ volume ratio in the interdiffusion zone	0.52
(Cr,Co)Sb content in (Co,Cr)Sb₂ layer [vol%]	6.0

Moreover, some inward diffusion of chromium could contribute to further development of the interdiffusion zone. If the (Cr,Co)Sb formed by bonding antimony released during the decomposition of CoSb₃ to CoSb₂, thickness of the dense (Co,Cr)Sb₂ layer can be estimated on the basis of thickness of the (Cr,Co)Sb layer. Co-doping of CrSb up to 10 at.% does not significantly change the *a* and *c* lattice parameters at room temperature [66]. According to the calculations, if both layers have crystallographic density of CrSb and CoSb₂, the thickness of the (Co,Cr)Sb₂ layer should be about 150% that of (Cr,Co)Sb, which gives the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ thickness ratio of about 0.67. However, for the samples annealed shortly this ratio is higher, and then it decreases with the annealing time. Finally it

calculated from the slope of the regression lines in Fig. 15a–c. The values of *k* with standard deviation and the related adjusted coefficient of determination R^2_{adj} are summarized in Table 3. High values of R^2_{adj} (higher than 0.96 with one exception) indicate good correlation of the experimental data with the parabolic rate law and confirm that the growth of the layers is diffusion-controlled within the studied temperature range.

In [67] the structure of CoSb₃ formed by reactive diffusion from pure solids, antimony and cobalt, was investigated at 550 °C. To compare the results, based on the data from Ref. [67] the parabolic rate constants for the growth of CoSb₂ and CoSb₃ layers were estimated as $\sim 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\sim 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, which appeared in good agreement with the values obtained in this study for the CoSb₂ layer growth.

Temperature dependence of the parabolic rate constants in the Arrhenius plot (Fig. 16) allowed determining the activation energy *Q*. The corresponding values with the standard deviations and R^2_{adj} are given in Table 4.

4. Discussion

According to the available binary phase diagrams for the Co–Sb and Cr–Sb systems [65,68–70], CrSb, CrSb₂, CoSb, CoSb₂ and Co₂CrSb can be present in the Cr–CoSb₃ diffusion couple, however, only the first four were identified in this work. Selected properties of the mentioned antimonides are listed in Table 1.

In the first stage the interdiffusion zone formed mainly as a result of an outward diffusion of antimony and its reaction with chromium at the Cr/CoSb₃ interface. The solubility of antimony in chromium at 600 °C is lower than 5 at. % and above this level chromium antimonides could appear as a result of chemical reactions [68]:

and/or

Fig. 12. 3D reconstruction of a) (Cr,Co)Sb, b) pores and cracks.

Fig. 13. Cross-sections of the selected Cr–CoSb₂ diffusion couples presenting evolution of the interdiffusion zone with time and temperature, SEM, BSE. Description “Cr layer” in the images corresponds to the initial chromium layer above the substrate surface.

becomes approximately constant, reaching the value of about 0.5 (200%) after 288 h at all experimental temperatures. Moreover, also the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ volume ratio in the interdiffusion zone, calculated on the basis of 3D tomography for the sample annealed at 600 °C for 24 h, is close to 0.5 (200%) (Table 2). It can be assumed

that the observed deviations arise not only from differences in crystallographic density of the layers. After short annealing times the (Co,Cr)Sb₂ layer was not detected in the interdiffusion zone. Therefore, it can be assumed that the following reaction took place in the initial step:

Fig. 14. Layer thickness vs. time in Cr–CoSb₃ diffusion couples at different temperatures (lines are drawn between points to illustrate trends).

For the reaction $\text{CoSb}_2 + \text{Cr} = \text{CrSb} + \text{CoSb}$ at 577 °C the Gibbs free energy $\Delta_r G^\circ$ equals -6.7 kJ [60]. The occurrence of this reaction can be confirmed by local appearance of (Co,Cr)Sb close to the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ interface in some specimens. Systematic analyses of the chemical composition indicated that (Co,Cr)Sb was an intermediate phase, detected in the diffusion couples annealed at 600 °C for 24 h, at 550 °C for 24 h and 72 h, at 500 °C for 72–288 h. Thus, the lower the annealing temperature, the longer the time when (Co,Cr)Sb was present in the interdiffusion zone. Since (Co,Cr)Sb occurred exclusively at the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ interface, it was not detected in specimens annealed shorter than 18 h, when CoSb₂ did not form.

CrSb and CoSb have the same crystallographic structure (Table 1) and can form solid solutions in the whole range of chemical composition [66], according to the reaction:

Growth of the (Cr,Co)Sb layer can also be a result of chromium diffusion into CoSb₃. Cobalt triantimonide is a stoichiometric compound and chromium solubility in CoSb₃ is limited to about 1 at.% [71]. In the CoSb₃ crystal lattice, chromium occupies cobalt positions [71]. Above the solubility limit, precipitation of cobalt and chromium antimonides should occur, e.g.:

For the reaction $\text{CoSb}_3 + \text{Cr} = \text{CrSb} + \text{CoSb}_2$ at 577 °C the Gibbs free energy $\Delta_r G^\circ$ equals -8.2 kJ [60].

Although, in view of the fact that formation of the (Co,Cr)Sb₂

layer was delayed and that intense sublimation of antimony from CoSb₃ takes place at elevated temperatures [72], it seems that formation of chromium antimonides in a direct reaction between Cr and CoSb₃ is not of significant importance. The layers that appear as a result of interdiffusion separate the CoSb₃ substrate from Cr and hinder an outward diffusion of antimony.

In the SEM-EDS measurements it could be noticed that for the shortly annealed specimens, the amount of cobalt in the (Cr,Co)Sb layer was rather low. Therefore, it is believed that in the early stages, a direct reaction between chromium and antimony was the principal process contributing to the formation of (Cr,Co)Sb.

The 3D tomography revealed that (Cr,Co)Sb grains present within the (Co,Cr)Sb₂ layer usually had no connection with the (Cr,Co)Sb layer. It might happen that these (Cr,Co)Sb grains were formed in the initial steps of the reaction according to [r3] and got separated from the (Cr,Co)Sb layer because the diffusion rate of antimony was higher than that of chromium. Another plausible explanation is that (Cr,Co)Sb precipitated along the CoSb₂ grain boundaries as a result of the limited solubility of Cr in CoSb₂ (in this study maximum measured concentration of Cr in CoSb₂ was about 2 at.%).

Due to the easy sublimation of antimony at elevated temperatures, the CoSb₃ grain boundaries gradually became depleted in antimony and locally enriched in cobalt. The defect structure of the CoSb₃ crystal lattice is not known but some inward diffusion of cobalt and outward diffusion of antimony might take place within the CoSb₃ grains. Moreover, diffusion of cobalt into CrSb or CrSb₂ is also possible and the solid solutions or lower antimonides could be formed, such as CoSb₂ or CoSb.

The non-uniform (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ interface and the presence of (Co,Cr)Sb close to the (Cr,Co)Sb/(Co,Cr)Sb₂ interface indicate that the grain boundary diffusion was the major transport process

Fig. 15. Layer thickness variations as a function of time in the interdiffusion zone of Cr–CoSb₃ couples presented in a parabolic co-ordinate system.

Table 3

Parabolic rate constants k with standard deviation and adjusted coefficient of determination R^2_{adj} calculated on the basis of experimental data for the (Co,Cr)Sb₂ and (Cr,Co)Sb layers.

Temperature [°C]	(Co,Cr)Sb ₂			(Cr,Co)Sb		
	k [cm ² s ⁻¹]	Standard deviation [cm ² s ⁻¹]	R^2_{adj}	k [cm ² s ⁻¹]	Standard deviation [cm ² s ⁻¹]	R^2_{adj}
500	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-14}$	0.99	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$9.4 \cdot 10^{-15}$	0.97
550	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.96	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$5.6 \cdot 10^{-14}$	0.87
600	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.99	$9.4 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$6.9 \cdot 10^{-14}$	0.97

Fig. 16. Arrhenius plot for the growth rate of layers in the interdiffusion zone.

Table 4

Activation energy (Q) of $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ and $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ layer growth with standard deviation and R^2_{adj} values.

	Q [kJ·mol ⁻¹]	Standard deviation [kJ·mol ⁻¹]	R^2_{adj}
$(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$	118.7	9.3	0.99
$(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$	114.5	11.9	0.98

in the investigated system. The values of parabolic rate constants, k , in Table 3 show that $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ grew faster than $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ and that the corresponding layer thickness ratio was approximately constant at each temperature. Thus, after some time the steady-state conditions were established and thickness of the layers was determined by the transport properties of these layers.

In some specimens, CrSb_2 was temporarily observed (Fig. 9a–c). For illustration, at 550 °C this phase was found in specimens annealed for 1 h and 3 h and in both cases it appeared together with $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$. At 600 °C after 3 h of annealing the interdiffusion zone was composed of $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ and CrSb_2 (Fig. 9a). When the annealing time was extended to 6 h or 12 h the interdiffusion zone was composed mainly of CrSb_2 (Fig. 9b and c) and after 24 h both $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ were detected (Fig. 2c). The sequence of formation and vanishing of chromium antimonides can be explained as follows: the CrSb phase was the first to form as a result of antimony diffusion outwards. At the temperature of 577 °C the standard Gibbs free energy of formation of CrSb , ΔG_f° , equals -17.4 kJ per 1 mol of antimony [60]. Further supply of antimony caused the development of CrSb_2 , ΔG_f° at 577 °C being -10.7 kJ per 1 mol of antimony [60]. The solubility limit of cobalt in CrSb_2 is not reported in literature. Moreover, since CrSb_2 is a stoichiometric compound, and cobalt was not detected in this phase by SEM-EDS analyses, it seems that diffusion of cobalt and antimony resulted in the formation of $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$. At 577 °C the Gibbs free energy $\Delta_r G^\circ$ for the reaction:

equals -13.4 kJ [60], and for the reaction:

it equals -34.7 kJ [60].

This sequence of reactions would explain an increased

concentration of cobalt in the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ phase in the specimens annealed for extended times.

5. Conclusions

The systematic investigations of the Cr-CoSb_3 diffusion couples were carried out taking advantage of the advanced techniques of analytical electron microscopy. It has been shown that vacuum annealing of the Cr-CoSb_3 diffusion couples in the temperature range 500 °C – 600 °C led to the formation of a layered interdiffusion zone consisting mostly of $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$; CrSb_2 and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}$ appeared temporarily in the specimens annealed shortly, i.e. before the steady-state conditions of layer growth were established. The kinetics of the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ layer growth could be described by a parabolic rate law, diffusion being the rate-determining step. Thickness of the layers was determined by the transport properties of these layers. The calculated values of activation energy for the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ and $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ layer growth are 114.4 kJ·mol⁻¹ and 118.7 kJ·mol⁻¹, respectively.

The following plausible explanation can be given for the development of the interdiffusion zone:

- I An outward diffusion of antimony and its direct reaction with chromium yield CrSb and CrSb_2 , which contribute to the initial formation of $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$
- II Antimony for this process comes from decomposition of CoSb_3 to CoSb_2 and Sb . However, the quantitative ratios of phases present in the interdiffusion zone indicate that also other reactions may be involved.
- III An inward diffusion of chromium triggers the subsequent transformation of CoSb_2 : $\text{CoSb}_2 + \text{Cr} \rightarrow (\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb} + (\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}$, can be confirmed by local appearance of $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}$ close to the $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}/(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ interface in some specimens and delayed formation of the CoSb_2 layer.
- IV Chromium antimonides might also form in a direct reaction between Cr diffusing inwards and CoSb_3 , but this process is not considered of significant importance.
- V The $(\text{Cr,Co})\text{Sb}$ occlusions within the $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{Sb}_2$ grains can be related to the limited solubility of Cr in CoSb_2 or a difference in diffusion rates of chromium and antimony.
- VI The sequence of appearance and vanishing of chromium antimonides can be explained as follows: first, the CrSb phase is formed as a result of an outward diffusion of antimony.; further supply of antimony causes its transformation

to CrSb₂; finally the solubility limits of chromium and antimony in CrSb₂ result in the formation of (Cr,Co)Sb.

VII Formation of the layered microstructure of the interdiffusion zone is a result of an inward diffusion of chromium and an outward diffusion of antimony.

For full understanding of the diffusion mechanism and reactions between individual phases present in the interdiffusion zone, further studies should be performed involving a series of simple diffusion couples consisting of cobalt and chromium antimonides with different stoichiometry.

Data statement

The raw/processed data that supports the findings of this study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Kinga Zawadzka: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition. **Elżbieta Godlewska:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Supervision. **Krzysztof Mars:** Resources. **Aleksandr Kryshstal:** Investigation. **Adam Kruk:** Visualization.

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